

Introducing dried spot techniques in food characterization: The case of red wine

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ABSTRACT

Food quality, interrogated by analytical methods, is a prerequisite of modern societies' well-being. However, analysis is greatly compromised at the sampling and sample preparation stages, which are typically resource-intensive and tedious. Dried spot microsampling on paper cards, used almost exclusively for dried blood spots (DBS) in biomedical settings, offers noteworthy advantages to conventional techniques, almost eliminating sample preparation amid easy on-site sampling. Moreover, it involves minute sample size and transportation by regular post, relieved from bulk sample requirements and questionable transfer and storage conditions. Dried spot techniques could thus provide an attractive solution to existing challenges for holistic food quality assessment, yet they remain unwarrantedly unexplored in this field. The present work introduces dried spot sampling of food commodities, or Food-DS, as an alternative format in food characterization, utilizing untargeted LC-HRMS as a powerful metabolite profiling tool. Using red wine as a proof-of-concept, an optimized workflow was developed for volumetric sampling on standard DBS cards followed by automated extraction and was successfully compared to conventional techniques. Various aspects were optimized for enhanced sensitivity and metabolite coverage, including spot extraction parameters and, notably, extraction solvent type, assisted by the dereplication results. The possibility of remote sampling by non-trained users, in conjunction with automated card processing, highlights the potential of the proposed workflow to promote accessible and cost-effective food analysis. This study is envisioned to serve as a basis for the integration of dried spot techniques in food characterization towards more convenient and resource-efficient quality assessment, minimizing logistical constraints.

1. Introduction

Advanced analytical techniques are required to effectively monitor the quality of foods and natural products in general, which are complex matrices containing various classes of compounds [1,2]. Nonetheless, the sampling and sample preparation steps remain typically resource-intensive and tedious, posing significant challenges in food analysis along the production and supply chains [3,4]. Also, the preparation of samples prior to analysis intending to extract the metabolite (s) of interest introduces additional steps and cost. On the other hand, dried spot microsampling on paper cards, which has been mostly used for dried blood spots (DBS) in biomedical applications such as newborn

screening [5,6], presents noteworthy advantages including minute sample size, easy on-site sampling even in remote areas, and convenient sample transportation via regular post [6,7] (Fig. 1). Dried spot techniques applied in food matrices or Food-DS may thus offer an attractive solution to current challenges in quality monitoring, significantly facilitating logistical aspects, among others. However, the dried spot format remains unwarrantedly underutilized in food analysis, and there have not yet been such applications in the characterization of food commodities for intrinsic quality assessment. Only very few reports exist that are relevant addressing targeted detection of exogenous compounds for safety issues. More specifically, in the work of Schlegel et al. [8], the authors employed dried spots of cereal extracts on DBS cards for

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targeted analysis of food contaminants (mycotoxins). Recently, in the work of Geballa-Koukoula et al. [9], the authors proposed a novel dried-spot based workflow for targeted contaminant (pesticide) monitoring in eggs and ornamental flowers. Still, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no reported dried spot-based methodologies for food commodities with a view to characterize their chemical composition.

Analysis of dried spot samples can be achieved through various separation and detection systems, depending on the molecular structure of the analytes, matrix complexity and sensitivity required. Liquid chromatography remains a predominant technique in dried spot analysis and is mostly coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS) due to its superior sensitivity and accuracy [5], though hyphenation with other detectors such as UV/DAD or ELSD may also be employed given the scope of the study. More recently, LC coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) is widely employed due to its high resolving power and accurate mass measurements, primarily for profiling approaches [10]. Especially, LC-HRMS/MS is a powerful platform for untargeted analysis, enabling the characterization of the complex chemical composition of food products, including the multiple classes of phenolic compounds [11]. The integration of dried spot sampling techniques in untargeted LC-HRMS/MS workflows for food analysis would thus enable comprehensive characterization of foods in a more resource-efficient manner. Targeted analysis is equally virtuous though requiring sensitive methods due to the inherently low sample amount on card [12,13].

Apart from the analytical platform, a key determinant of the efficiency of the entire workflow is the spot extraction process. Existing reports for biosamples typically involve manual detachment/punching of discs followed by extraction, which is laborious and prone to human error [14,15]. On the other hand, DBS cards are amenable to fully automated handling and extraction, and robotic systems are commercially available to this end [16,17], allowing the development of high-capacity workflows for food quality assessment, diminishing multiple steps and cost.

Based on the above, this work aims to introduce dried spot sampling

as an alternative format in food and drinks characterization or Food-DS. LC-HRMS/MS analysis under an untargeted concept was selected as the most suitable for workflow evaluation and optimization. Red wine as a global product subjected to rigorous quality control was selected as a proof-of-concept, initiating Food-DS or Wine-DS more specifically. Although mostly of aqueous nature, wine presents a highly complex chemical composition, especially in the case of red wine, whose moderate consumption has been associated with positive health effects [18–20]. As with other food/beverage matrices, the whole composition of wine impacts its sensory and health-related characteristics, calling for untargeted strategies to effectively explore quality attributes and address authenticity and traceability aspects [21–23]. To this end, an optimized dried spot-based workflow was developed for untargeted characterization by LC-HRMS, involving volumetric microsampling of red wine on standard DBS paper cards, followed by automated card handling and extraction. The dried spot methodology was compared to conventional sample preparation methods for wine, including benchmark filtration and dilution, assessing similarity of chemical profiles. Various parameters, including extraction solvent type, were optimized for the analysis of the wine dried spots (hereafter “Wine-DS”) in an untargeted context, evaluating extraction capacity and metabolite coverage, assisted by the dereplication results. A schematic overview of the dried spot-based approach of this work for red wine characterization is presented in Fig. 1.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

HPLC grade methanol (MeOH) and ethyl acetate (EtOAc) were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Leicestershire, UK) and Carlo Erba (Milan, Italy), respectively. Acetonitrile (ACN) of LC-MS grade (LiChrosolv®, Hypergrade) was obtained from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany), while LC-MS grade MeOH and formic acid were supplied from Fisher Chemical (Loughborough, UK). All aqueous solutions were prepared

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the developed dried spot or Food-DS methodology for untargeted characterization of wine, entailing microsampling on paper cards by capillary tubes (10 µL), automated extraction of the wine dried spots (Wine-DS) and untargeted LC-HRMS/MS profiling. Lower panel shows comparative base peak chromatograms [ESI(-)] of red wine sample processed with common conventional sample preparation technique (dilution 1:1 wine/H₂O) vs. via the optimized dried spot protocol (Section 2.3). The pie chart presents the distribution of chemical classes in the Wine-DS sample extracted with H₂O/ACN 80:20, based on peak areas of the 100 annotated metabolites.

with ultrapure water (18.2 M Ω ·cm) produced by a Milli-Q purification system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany).

Untreated grade 226 Perkin Elmer Bioanalysis RUO filter paper (pure cellulose) cards (Revvity Health Sciences Inc., Massachusetts, USA) were used. Glass capillary tubes with ring mark (5, 10 and 20 μ L) were provided by Hirschmann Laborgeräte (Eberstadt, Germany). Commercial red wine “Barbasaina”, a multivarietal European Union wine, was purchased from a local supermarket in Greece.

2.2. Automated DBS card extraction system

Automated extraction of the wine dried spots (Wine-DS) was performed using the commercially available DBS AutosamplerTM (DBSA, Spark Holland, Emmen, The Netherlands), comprising modules for robotic handling of DBS cards and automated spot extraction by flow-through desorption with the aid of a high-pressure dispenser pump (HPD) [24,25]. The system was operated using the CHRONOS software (Axel Semrau, Spockhövel, Germany). The extraction module comprised an extraction head with two different clamp options, a 4-mm diameter for partial spot extraction, and an 8-mm clamp for whole spot extraction. The extraction solvent was heated at 40 °C, using the available capillary, and was delivered at a predetermined volume and flow rate to the clamped area of the card. After each extraction, the system was washed with rinsing solution of the same type as the respective extraction solvent, purged through a blank area of the card. For more details see Supplementary data (Section S1).

2.3. Development of dried spot methodology for wine characterization

For the volumetric wine application on the DBS cards, glass capillary tubes were filled up to the ring mark with an accurate sample volume, which was delivered at the mid-point of the collection area of the card. Different volumes (5, 10 and 20 μ L) of red wine were tested. Development of the automated extraction process for the Wine-DS involved optimization of important parameters, including size of clamp head, extraction solvent volume and flow rate, and most notably, extraction solvent composition, in an untargeted context. In each case, the collected eluent was reconstituted before chromatographic analysis, and the respective conditions were also optimized. For repeatability aspects evaluation, certain peaks were selected covering an extended range of retention time (RT) and relative abundance. For more information, refer to Supplementary Section S1.

The final proposed protocol was the following: a volume of 10 μ L of red wine was volumetrically applied on DBS cards via capillary tube. Subsequently, upon drying for at least two hours at room temperature, automated card handling and whole spot extraction followed using H₂O/ACN 80:20 as extraction solvent, at a volume of 1000 μ L and a flow rate of 500 μ L/min. The resulting extract was collected, evaporated to dryness, reconstituted in 50 μ L of H₂O/MeOH 80:20 and analyzed by LC-HRMS/MS for untargeted characterization.

Conventional sample preparation techniques for wine LC analysis were performed in parallel for comparison purposes, including the most minimal ones, i.e., dilution (1:1 in H₂O) and filtration (0.45 μ m PVDF), in addition to solid-phase extraction (SPE), and liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) (see Supplementary Section S2).

2.4. UPLC – HRMS/MS analysis

Chromatographic analysis was performed on an H class Acquity UPLC system (Waters, USA) interfaced to a Velos Pro-Orbitrap Elite hybrid mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Inc., USA) with heated electrospray ionization (HESI-II) source. Xcalibur software v.3.0.63 (Thermo Scientific) was used for data acquisition and processing. Chromatographic separation was conducted on an Ascentis Express C18 column (100 \times 2.1 mm, 2 μ m) (Supelco, Bellefonte, USA). Column temperature was set at 40 °C, while the autosampler compartment was

thermostated at 10 °C. A gradient elution program was employed comprising water with 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B), delivered at a flow rate of 0.2 mL/min. Elution began with 98 % A for the first 1.5 min and a gradient from 98 to 60 % A was set in the next 16.5 min. In the following 7 min, the composition of A was further decreased to 0 % and held isocratically for 2 min. Finally, the initial mobile phase composition was restored over the next 0.5 min and maintained for the last 2.5 min for column re-equilibration. The total run time was 30 min. Injection volume was 10 μ L for all samples.

Mass spectra were obtained using an *m/z* range of 113,00 – 1000,00 Da for full scan acquisition, at a resolving power of 120,000 (full width half maximum, FWHM, at 400 *m/z*). For untargeted profiling of all samples, the negative ESI mode was selected. HRMS/MS spectra were recorded using data-dependent acquisition (FS-dd-MS²) with a collision energy of 35.0 % (*q*=0.25) and a resolving power of 60,000 at 400 *m/z*. Optimal HRMS parameters chosen were the following: capillary and source heater temperatures were set at 350 °C, source voltage at 3.6 kV and S-lens RF level at 60 %. Sheath and auxiliary gases were appointed at 45 and 15 arbitrary units, respectively.

2.5. Data processing and metabolite annotation

The raw data files from the acquisition software (Xcalibur) were processed utilizing MZmine 2.53. The tools for mass detection (centroid mass detector) and chromatogram building (Automated Data Analysis Pipeline – ADAP) were used. Chromatogram deconvolution was performed with the local minimum search algorithm, followed by deisotoping (isotopic peaks grouper), alignment (join aligner algorithm), and gap filling (peak finder algorithm). The generated peak list was manually filtered to remove chemically irrelevant information, resulting in a table of 468 molecular features which was used for the untargeted profiling of wine. To ensure comparability among the different sample preparation methods, peak areas were normalized to reflect equal initial sample (wine) volume. Heatmap analysis was performed in the MetaboAnalyst 6.0 online platform using the dataset of annotated features as individual metabolites to visualize the differences among the samples. Finally, specific graphs were plotted using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism v9.0.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., CA, USA).

Metabolite annotation was manually performed considering chromatographic information, recorded elemental composition by accurate mass measurement (mass error \pm 5 ppm), unsaturation degree (RBD equivalents), and HRMS/MS fragmentation pattern in negative ESI mode. The obtained results were compared with published data for wine metabolome, publicly available databases, including FoodDB (<http://foodb.ca/>), MassBank (www.massbank.jp) and METLIN (metlin.scripps.edu), and in-house developed databases.

3. Results and discussion

This work introduces dried spot sampling in food characterization or Food-DS as an advantageous alternative format, which has been unjustifiably underutilized in food analysis, despite the potential to overcome critical challenges. The use of paper card as a collection device may offer key advantages for food quality control, notably simplified logistics and sampling. The dried spot format enables easy, low-volume, on-site sampling without specialized equipment, eliminates the need for cold storage, and allows cost-effective transport via regular mail. By incorporating these features, it may reduce costs, minimize spoilage risk, support traceability and remote sampling by non-trained individuals, thus facilitating general applicability and contributing to efficient food quality characterization.

Using red wine as a proof-of-concept, a dried spot-based workflow was developed for convenient sampling on standard DBS cards, followed by automated extraction using a robotic system, and untargeted characterization by LC-HRMS. Although there are works exploring diet-related (bio)markers in dried spots mostly of hematic matrices, such

as [13,26], there only very few works that have employed DBS cards for sampling food commodities [8,9], and these involved targeted investigation of specific contaminants, not innate constituents, in extracts either of cereal-based foodstuffs [8] or eggs/ornamental flowers [9]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the present work describes for the first time a dried spot-based methodology for the untargeted characterization of food commodities, introducing a novel approach in food analysis, Food-DS.

Conventional sample preparation techniques for LC-based analysis of wine were initially applied to the representative wine sample to serve as a basis for comparison with the dried spot methodology. These included minimal techniques, i.e., filtration and dilution, which are typically used in untargeted characterization approaches for wine [21,27,28]. Additional reported techniques for wine, i.e., LLE and SPE with two types of sorbents (C18 and HLB), were performed to complement the panel of conventional sample treatments [29–31]. Different chromatographic profiles were obtained, especially when the SPE and LLE were involved (Supplementary Fig. S4), highlighting selectivity aspects in those processes, as was observed in the distribution of extracted metabolites grouped in chemical classes (Fig. S5). Based on the above, the simpler non-specific techniques (filtration and dilution) were selected for a more realistic comparison with the dried spot-based methodology during its development.

The Food-DS setup for red wine characterization was initiated with the establishment of a spot application technique for practical and reproducible on-site sampling of wine even by non-trained users in remote locations. The most appropriate sample volume was found to be 10 μ L, spotted using glass capillary tubes with predefined mark, enabling convenient and volumetric sampling. This volume was the maximum that could be applied in a single step, filling the premarked collection area on the card. The proposed sample volume for wine, although seemingly low, is consistent with standard injection volumes in direct LC-MS wine analysis [19,28]. Generally, the low sample volume

capacity reflects a known constraint of the DBS format, but this was effectively addressed through the development of a highly sensitive method using HRMS/MS detection.

Method development further involved the optimization of the automated extraction procedure, and notably the type of extraction solvent, considering extraction capacity and metabolome coverage, based on untargeted LC-HRMS/MS analysis. Several aspects were carefully optimized to increase sensitivity and cover a wide range of metabolites. This is of critical importance for comprehensive characterization efforts considering the intricately complex chemical composition of foods, including red wine, and the contribution of even minor constituents to important quality attributes [10,21]. Given that the proposed scheme was developed for wine, matrix-specific optimization may be needed in other food types, considering the inherent volume limitation, with a view to analyzing trace-level compounds besides the abundant ones.

The automated extraction of spots was initially performed using the system's configuration for partial spot extraction (4-mm clamp head), whereby various extraction solvents, including ACN and MeOH mixtures, were examined under fixed extraction parameters. In order to evaluate the repeatability of the extraction system, which is important for reliable results, certain peaks were selected and monitored. Specifically, these were chosen to span a range of RT and a gradient of abundances. Percent relative standard deviation (RSD) values below 5 % were obtained, verifying the good performance of the extraction procedure (Table S1). However, due to poor peak shape and overall chromatographic profiles of the obtained reconstituted extracts, it was decided to proceed with whole spot extraction, which was achieved by utilizing the clamp head of maximum diameter (8 mm). By further finetuning the automated extraction parameters, including extraction solvent volume and delivery flow rate, in conjunction with optimization of extract reconstitution before chromatographic analysis (see Section 2.3), a significant increase in sensitivity was achieved (see Fig. S1). This strategy enabled effectively tapping into the wealth of chemical

Fig. 2. Number of detected molecular features per abundance level (normalized peak areas) by untargeted LC-HRMS in a multivarietal red wine through Wine-DS extracted with different solvents (H₂O, H₂O/ACN 80:20, ACN/H₂O 80:20 and MeOH/H₂O 80:20), and conventional sample preparation (filtration, dilution 1:1 in H₂O).

information in each dried spot (Wine-DS) despite the small sample volume (10 μ L). More details on method optimization can be found in Supplementary data (Section S1).

Further, based on the finetuned extraction and analytical parameters for optimized sensitivity, a panel of extraction solvents, i.e. H₂O, H₂O/ACN 80:20, ACN/H₂O 80:20 and MeOH/H₂O 80:20, were evaluated in terms of magnitude of analytical response, metabolite coverage, profile repeatability and extraction capacity. These were compared to conventional sample preparation methods for wine, particularly the simplest ones, i.e., filtration and dilution (1:1 wine/H₂O), after normalization of the LC-HRMS raw abundances to initial wine volume to ensure comparability. At first, the distribution of detected molecular features according to abundance level (Fig. 2) was evaluated, whereby relatively similar results were obtained for most examined Wine-DS extraction solvents and the common conventional methods. Among them, upon closer examination, the most promising solvents were H₂O/ACN 80:20, ACN/H₂O 80:20 and neat H₂O, providing large number of metabolite sets with high intensity, while MeOH/H₂O 80:20 showed relatively inferior extraction performance. Interestingly, regarding the conventional methods, wine dilution (1:1) yielded a larger number of features with high abundance than filtration, in congruence with previous findings from untargeted analysis of wine [28,32]. As can be observed in the comparative LC-HRMS chromatograms (Fig. S2), the filtered sample showed poorer peak resolution, conceivably due to the presence of ethanol in wine (~12 % v/v), and potential signal suppression. In that context, dilution was selected as the benchmark technique for comparison with the proposed dried spot-based process, considering also the wide adoption of the former in LC-MS analysis of various food matrices besides wine [33].

To explore the chemical intricacies on a more meaningful level, a dereplication strategy was followed using the LC-ESI(-)-HRMS/MS data for the detailed characterization of the multivarietal red wine. This process resulted in the tentative identification of 100 metabolites (Supplementary Section S3, Table S2) which spanned a range of chemical classes, including organic acids, phenolic acids (hydroxybenzoic and hydroxycinnamic acids), flavonoids (flavonols, flavanols, sulfonated flavonoids, proanthocyanidins), as well as other classes such as stilbenoids, fatty acids and amino acids. A typical ESI(-) base peak

chromatogram of the studied red wine with annotated peaks for metabolites of relatively high abundance is given in Supplementary data (Fig. S6). The chemical characterization results were in line with previous findings regarding red wine [19,34]. To progress the optimization of the dried spot-based extraction methodology, peak areas of the annotated metabolites in the representative red wine were summed, allowing an overview of the extraction capacity according to chemical class for the Wine-DS with different extraction solvents in comparison with conventional sample preparation (dilution) (Fig. 3).

As can be observed, Wine-DS provides similar results to the conventional method, with subtle differences in extraction efficiency and selectivity according to extraction solvent, showing the H₂O/ACN mixtures as the most promising for non-selective extraction. To further probe the subtle differences among the solvents in terms of selectivity and establish the most appropriate technique for the global characterization of red wine constituents, a heatmap was generated using the normalized peak intensities of the annotated metabolites. The heatmap visualization (Fig. 4) allowed for a more nuanced comparison, considering the contribution of also minor constituents for holistic food quality characterization. Irrespective of the extraction solvent in the Wine-DS, a good profile repeatability was achieved between replicates, highlighting the consistency of the dried spot-based procedure. In parallel, analysis of the results from spot re-extraction with the same solvent indicated the efficiency of the Wine-DS extraction procedure and corroborated the overall good performance of H₂O/ACN 80:20 (Fig. S3).

Subtle differences in selectivity can be observed in the heatmap of Fig. 4. Interestingly, MeOH/H₂O 80:20 seemed to have lower extraction capacity for some clusters of compounds, notably flavanols, sulfonated flavonoids, and proanthocyanidins, confirming the observations of the more limited extraction capacity of this solvent system for Wine-DS. As regards neat H₂O, despite its obvious advantages in terms of environmental friendliness, it showed weaker extraction efficiency for a specific panel of compounds, mostly flavonols such as quercetin (the major flavonol in the sample), myricetin and kaempferol, providing a slightly distorted profile in comparison with benchmark sample preparation (Fig. 5). Taken together, H₂O/ACN 80:20 displayed the most promising results, showing a more accurate and unbiased profile, similarly to ACN/H₂O 80:20. Considering multiple aspects, including environmental

Fig. 3. Distribution of compound classes in the studied red wine based on the sum of normalized LC-HRMS peak areas of the annotated 100 metabolites grouped per class, as obtained by Wine-DS extracted with different solvents (H₂O, H₂O/ACN 80:20, ACN/H₂O 80:20 and MeOH/H₂O 80:20) and by conventional wine dilution (1:1 wine/H₂O).

Fig. 4. Heatmap of the annotated compounds showing their relative abundance among the different extraction solvents (H₂O, H₂O/ACN 80:20, ACN/H₂O 80:20 and MeOH/H₂O 80:20) of the Wine-DS (two replicates) and conventional sample preparation methods, i.e., filtration and dilution 1:1 (Ward's algorithm with Euclidean distance, no scaling).

impact, the mixture with the higher aqueous content, i.e., H₂O/ACN 80:20 was finally selected as extraction solvent for the red wine dried spots. Overall, the proposed dried spot-based workflow for red wine untargeted characterization, including spot application and automated extraction mode, followed by proper reconstitution was successfully juxtaposed to benchmark sample preparation, i.e., direct injection of diluted (1:1) wine. Indeed, high similarity in metabolite profiles yielded with the optimized methodology described in this work and the conventional dilution was achieved (Fig. 5), as can be observed in the respective base peak LC-HRMS chromatograms and pie charts (Fig. 1, Fig. S5) showing the relative distribution of metabolites aggregated according to chemical class.

Regarding analyte stability, exposure of Wine-DS to ambient laboratory conditions during the drying phase (~2 h) and subsequent short-

term storage until analysis (up to a few days) did not seem to induce noticeable alterations in chemical profiles compared to minimally treated fresh samples (simple dilution). This may indicate that wine spotted on DBS cards remains chemically stable over a typical timeframe that would allow for sample transport to analytical facilities via regular post. Although the dried spot format reportedly seems to improve analyte stability in biological matrices [35,36], comprehensive stability studies using various wines are needed to fully validate the proposed novel application of dried spot techniques in a new matrix (wine), including long-term stability assessment.

To sum up, the proposed dried spot methodology provides similar results to benchmark conventional sample preparation methods for wine, while offering at the same time convenient sample collection, transportation and processing, towards more accessible quality

Fig. 5. LC-HRMS chromatograms (base peak, negative ion mode) for the comparison of conventional sample preparation (wine dilution 1:1) with the developed Wine-DS method employing the proposed H₂O/ACN 80:20, in addition to H₂O, as extraction solvents under optimized parameters (See Section 2.3).

assessment. The easy on-site sampling on standard DBS cards followed by integration into a fully automated extraction system, as undertaken in this work, minimizes resource consumption and human intervention steps, enabling cost-effective and high-capacity workflows. The developed dried spot-based methodology for food characterization by untargeted LC-HRMS, introduced herein for red wine, is foreseen to open new avenues for comprehensive analysis of other foods/beverages amid simplified logistics, following proper extrapolation. However, one limitation of this format is that more intricate adaptations may be required for solid foodstuffs, depending on the matrix type, since an additional initial extraction step is required to present the analytes into the paper card in an appropriate form for analysis.

4. Conclusion

In this work, the dried spot microsampling format, which is established for biofluids in biomedical applications, was introduced for the characterization of food commodities to facilitate quality assessment, especially logistical issues. Using red wine as a proof-of-concept, an efficient dried spot workflow was established for untargeted characterization by LC-HRMS, and was successfully compared to benchmark conventional techniques, providing similar metabolite profiles. The developed methodology involves easy volumetric sampling of only 10 μ L of wine on standard DBS paper cards in conjunction with automated card handling and extraction, fostering high-capacity food analysis. Various experimental parameters were optimized to obtain high sensitivity and metabolite coverage through the dried spot technique, whereby whole spot extraction with H₂O/ACN 80:20 yielded the most promising results in an untargeted context. The proposed dried spot-based approach for food characterization offers reproducibility, cost-effectiveness, and, most importantly, drastically facilitated logistics, featuring easy on-site sampling by non-trained users even in remote locations, and convenient sample transportation by regular post. Overall, this study presents a novel framework in food analysis, and although

starting from red wine, it is foreseen to serve as a basis for the dried spot-based characterization of other food commodities towards holistic, accessible and resource-efficient quality assessment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ioanna Deli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petros S. Tzimas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stavros Beteinakis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maria Halabalaki:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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